

KAZAKH-POLISH LITERARY RELATIONS

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The article deals with the literary relations between Kazakhstan and Poland. The process of literary translation of the works of Kazakh writers and poets into Polish from the second half of the XX century to the present is presented. Particular attention is paid to the prefaces and afterwords in the books published in Poland by A.Kunanbayev, I.Esenberlin, O.Suleimenov. The authors of the receptive material are Polish literary critics H. Jankowski, St. Kaluzhinski, E. Chapleevich.

Keywords: international relations, Kazakh literature, literary translation.

The history of Kazakh-Polish literary relations begins with the works of Polish revolutionaries who were exiled in Kazakhstan in the XIX century. Then for active participation in the Polish national liberation uprisings of 1830-1831, 1848-1849 Gustav Zelinsky, Adolf Yanushkevich and Bronislav Zalessky were exiled to Siberia and Kazakhstan. The poet G.Zelinsky was exiled to Siberia in 1838, "he visited Omsk, Tobolsk and the Kazakh steppe – Balkhash and Semirechye" [1, p. 37], his poems "The Kazakh" and "The Steppe" are dedicated to the Kazakh people. The poet and ethnographer A.Yanushkevich is the author of the book "Diaries and letters from a journey through the Kazakh steppes", which is a valuable source on ethnography, history and culture of the Kazakh people in the XIX century. The writer and artist B. Zalessky "had to spend anguishing years of exile in Orenburg and Mangyshlak" [1, p. 48]. He participated in scientific expeditions to Karatau and the Aral Sea, wrote the book "Polish Exiles in Orenburg" and published the album "Life of the Kyrgyz Steppes". The significance of the album in literary terms is determined by the explanatory texts for each of the 22 paintings: "the author describes the area or the architectural monument which is depicted on it, or talks about the customs and life of the Kazakhs, about legends and tales heard during wanderings through the steppes" [1, p. 50].

The literary translation influences on the development of international literary relations. It is considered an effective way for the author to immerse in a foreign language environment. This process developed most intensively during the Soviet period. Most of the translations of the works of Kazakh writers into Polish were carried out in the second half of the XX century, starting from the 1950s. During these years, the novels "Soldier from Kazakhstan" (1951) by Gabit Musrepov, "Millionaire" (1951) by Gabiden Mustafin, "Botagoz" (1951) by Sabit Mukanov were published in Poland during these years. It is noteworthy that Gabit Musrepov's book includes a preface, which presents the writer's autobiography and his creativity: "In fiction, the author gives a fascinating picture of the deep social

changes in the country, writes about collectivization, industrialization, and cultural development" [2, p. 322].

In the series "Biblioteka dla dzieci" ("Library for Children") in 1951, Sapargali Begalin's book "Kid Seyid's Camel" [3] was published in the translation of Zofia Lapicka. S.Begalin is a famous Kazakh children's writer, and the characters of his stories are young shepherds and hunters who help the adults.

Zhambyl Zhabayev's poems "Dzhambul listens to Lenin", "On the death of the son", "In Lenin's Mausoleum" were published in Warsaw in the magazines "Przyjaźń" (1947), "Tribuna wolności" (1949), "Wies" (1952), "Poprostu" (1952). Polish newspapers and magazines published articles about the Kazakh poet "Dzhambul Zhabayev – the singer of Kazakhstan" by L.Rubakh [4], Z.Ziki "The Great Akyn of Kazakhstan" [5]. Brief biographical information about him is included into the Polish encyclopedia "Leksykon PWN", published in 1972 in Warsaw by the "State Scientific Publishing House" ("Państwowe Wydawnictwo Naukowe"), which published encyclopedias, dictionaries, scientific papers.

From the works of the classic of the Kazakh literature Mukhtar Auezov, both books of the epic novel "The Path of Abai" were published and republished in Polish. In the first edition, two books of the novel were published under the title "Abai – Son of Kazakhstan" [6] in 1950 and 1951. Translator – S. Pogorzelski. The second edition of the novel entitled "The Path of Abay" [7] was published in 1954 in the translation of M. Dub. In 1961, the story "Grey Fierce" was published in the Polish weekly magazine "Pshekrui" [8] and in the collection "Star fall and other stories of the contemporary writers" [9].

In the 1970s and 1980s, in Poland the works of the Kazakhstani writer Maurice Simashko have been quite actively translated into Polish. In 1974, the novel "The Magician from the Temple of Fire" [10], translated by Jiri Litvinyuk, was published in Warsaw in the "Klub Interesującej Książki" ("Interesting Books Club") series. In Russian, this work is known as the novel "Mazdak". In the same year, the Czytelnik publishing house published the book "Yemshan. Stories of the Red and

Black Sands” [11]. Translation into Polish was done by Jiri Litvinyuk and Robert Stiller. In 1983, the historical novel “Dabir’s Debt” [12] with an afterword by Maria Skladankova, and in 1989, the story “Gu-ga” [13] translated by Michal Jagiello were published.

Prefaces and afterword in the books, which were published abroad are an important factor in foreign literary reception. Thus, the book “Nomads” [14] by Ilyas Esenberlin, published in Warsaw in 1982, includes a foreword by Stanislaw Kaluzhinski. The Polish orientalist demonstrates extensive knowledge of Mongolian studies, citing some historical facts related to the history of the peoples on the territory of modern Kazakhstan after the formation of the Mongol Empire. The book “Nomads” is the first part of the eponymous historical trilogy, which tells about the life of the Kazakhs from the XV to the middle of the XIX century. In the first part of the trilogy, special attention is paid to the actions of the Kazakh Khans Janibek and Kerey, who separated from Khan Abulkhair, to whom many Turkic tribes were subject in the XVIII century. St. Kaluzhinski describes the process of division of power in the steppes of Kazakhstan between the sons and grandsons of the Mongol Khan Genghis Khan, so as to understand the numerous plots of the novel and frequent references to earlier times. By the way, the Khans Abulkhair, Janibek and Kerey were descendants of Jochi (the eldest son of Genghis Khan). Most of the characters in the novel are famous historical figures. St. Kaluzhinski notes that “the personalities of the rulers or steppe leaders are depicted very colorfully, brightly, convincingly, regardless of the fact which side the author’s sympathies are on” [14, p. 12]. Calling the work of I. Esenberlin a successful novel that is worth reading, St. Kaluzhinski praises it highly: “The author develops many plots of the novel in such a way that it arouses keen interest. Excellent knowledge of historical sources, as well as the nomadic way of life, perhaps from his own life experience or at least from a thorough study of it, combined with the undoubted excellence of the writer, allowed him to portray a colorful panorama of civil strife, conflicts and battles, social problems, as well as interesting phenomena of life among the Turkic tribes on the territory of Kazakhstan” [14, p. 13].

In recent years, the establishment and development of international relations in culture and literature has been taking place on the background of the intensification of Kazakhstani international relations in all areas of our country’s life. With gaining independence, the scale of integration of Kazakh literature into the world artistic process has increased.

In the development of Kazakh-Polish literary relations during the period of independence of Kazakhstan, the creativity of Abai Kunanbayev plays an important role. His poetic works and prose essay were translated into Polish three times. In 1996, in Warsaw, the publishing house “Przegląd Orientalistyczny” published the poem “Masgut” by Abai Kunanbayev translated into Polish by Malgorzata Labecka-Kocherova. In 2008, “Words of Edification” and poems by Abai Kunanbayev were translated into Polish by Raisa Yukhnievich and published in Astana with her foreword.

In 2013, “Words of Edification” was translated by Henryk Jankowski, a Polish linguist, orientalist, turkologist, Ph.D., researcher at the Adam Mickiewicz University in Poznan.

The book “Abaj Kunanbajuly. Słowa” [15] includes a foreword by H. Jankowski, which is consisting of two parts: “Abai and his creativity” and “Words”. In the first part, the author of the preface calls Abai the founder of written Kazakh literature: “Abai was the first great master of the word, whose creations were written down during his lifetime, although they were published after the author’s death. Thanks to this, they were preserved in written form” [16, p. 212]. Noting that long before Abai, Kazakh literature existed only in oral form, H. Jankowski tells Polish readers about the traditions of oral creativity of the Kazakh people. He mentions the names of famous storytellers of the XVI-XIX centuries as an example: Dospambet, Shalkiyiz, Zhyembet, Aktamberdy and others. For the first time, Abai’s poems were published after his death in 1909 in St. Petersburg, in 1916 – in Orenburg. The first complete edition of his works was published in Kyzyl-Orda in 1933. Today, Abai’s creative writings are available in various publications, including on the Internet.

H. Jankowski devoted the second part of the preface to Abai Kunanbaev’s philosophical essay “Words of Edification”, which consists of 45 chapters. H. Jankowski believes that in terms of content, “the chapters are of moralizing, educational, philosophical, socio-political, educational, religious and theological character. Chapter 1 presents the motives for writing this work. Some chapters are written in the form of a tale with a moral” [16, p. 214]. The author of the preface characterizes the style of the “Words” as essayistic or moralistic, using very expressive elements, and in some places narrative as well. In the “Words” there are many proverbs and sayings, as well as short fragments of speech connected by rhyme and rhythm. H. Jankowski pays attention to the repeated translation of this work into Russian, and through it into other languages: English, French, German, Chinese. H. Jankowski made a direct translation from Kazakh into Polish, without using the previous translation by R. Yukhnievich. Addressing Polish readers, he describes the political situation in the Kazakh steppe of that specific period, when Abai lived, which should be taken into account when reading the “Words”. H. Jankowski writes: “Abai lived in a period of collision of two worlds: traditional, largely nomadic world of Kazakh culture and the world of entrepreneurship of more educated Russian settlers, who had military and administrative support from the tsarist authorities. Under the influence of this collision, Kazakh culture began to change, be subjected to Russian influence, which was often adopted in a deformed form. The Kazakhs were at a crossroads. Their traditional way of life no longer met the requirements of the time” [16, p. 216]. According to H. Jankowski, in this kind of message, Abai appears as a moralizer who is trying to show the right way of behavior to the Kazakhs.

M.O. Auezov Institute of Literature and Art occupies an important place in the field of scientific study of the international relations of Kazakh literature. The staff of the Department of International Relations and

World Literature prepared and published the collections "The World of Auezov" (2004), "The World of Nurpeissov" (2006), "The World of Olzhas Suleimenov" (2015), "The Creativity of Abai Kunanbayev in Foreign Reception" (2016), "Literature of Kazakhstan in foreign sources" (2021). These collections include articles by foreign researchers on the creative writings of Kazakh writers and poets, translated from various foreign languages. The receptive material is systematized and presented in sections according to the countries. The section "Poland" is found in the collections "The World of Olzhas Suleimenov", "The Creativity of Abai Kunanbayev in Foreign Reception", "Literature of Kazakhstan in Foreign Sources". Publications by Polish authors were introduced into scientific circulation for the first time.

The collection "The World of Olzhas Suleimenov" includes a preface to Olzhas Suleimenov's poem "The Clay Book", which was published in Warsaw in 2009. "The Clay Book" is a poem about the love of Ishpakhan, who was the leader of the Scythian tribe Ish-Kuz and his concubine, the temple priestess Shamkhat. Then the author of the book held a presentation of his work at Warsaw University, the Polish Press Agency, and gave an interview to "Polskie Radio".

The author of the detailed preface is Eugeniusz Chapleevich, professor at Warsaw University, theorist and critic of literature, head of the Department of Theory and History of Literature of the A.Geishtor Academy of Humanities. In the preface by E. Chapleevich "Modern Kazakh epic of Olzhas Suleimenov. Unusual poetry, unusual poet, unusual poem" the analysis of the poem "The Clay Book" precedes the review of the Kazakh poetry of the pre-Soviet period and the biography of the Kazakh poet. E. Chapleevich focuses on the similarities and differences in the literature of the Kazakhs and the Polish. Speaking about the descriptions of nature and life in the steppe in Kazakh oral art, he finds similar descriptions of the culture of shepherds in the tetralogy "On the High Polonyna" by the Polish writer Stanislaw Vincenz. E. Chapleevich defines the specifics of the nomadic culture of the Kazakhs in the aura of freedom and liberty, in "the excess of space, which cannot be embraced and defined otherwise than only with the help of time" [17, p. 23]. Presenting the biography and creativity of O. Suleimenov, the author of the preface expresses his positive attitude towards the poet and thinker in the following words: which, freely managing various forms, styles, contexts, is ready at any time to break out of the limits of what he created" [17, p. 25]. During the analysis of the "Clay Book", such feature of perception of the poem of the Kazakh poet by European literary critic is manifested as comparison with similar works of Polish authors – the epic of Juliusz Slovatsky "King – Spirit" and the historical epic of Maciej Strykowski "On the beginnings, origins, deeds of the Lithuanian, Polish, Zhmudsky knight peoples ...". At the same time, E. Chapleevich notes that O. Suleimenov's poem is a modern poetic epic, created by a modern style; it has many paradoxes, stylization, understatement.

The collection "Creativity of Abai Kunanbayev in foreign reception" includes the above-mentioned prefaces by R. Yukhnievich and H. Jankowski.

In the collection "Literature of Kazakhstan in Foreign Sources", Polish sources are presented with an afterword from the book "Soldier from Kazakhstan" by G. Musrepov, a preface by the Polish poetess, prose writer, member of the Union of Writers of Poland Alicia Maria Kuberska from the poetry collection "Miniatures" by the Kazakhstani poet Stanislav Li (2019, Warsaw) and an article by Tomasz Veselovsky "«Penalty Boxes» – Personnel of the Red Army of 1940-1945" (2020) about the story "Gu-ga" by M. Simashko.

Electronic encyclopedias of various search engines on the Internet are interesting. The universal encyclopedia "Wikipedia" contains extensive articles in many languages on the life and creativity of Abai Kunanbayev. A short article about him is presented in Polish with reference to the encyclopedia "Pisarze świata: słownik encyklopedyczny" (Wydawnictwo Naukowe PWN Warszawa, 1995, p.11). Biographical information about the great Kazakh poet Abai Kunanbayev, published in foreign encyclopedias and posted on Internet encyclopedias, contributes to the popularization of his name and creative writings in the world literary space.

In Kazakhstan, the creativity of Polish exiles is studied in the context of Kazakh-Polish literary relations. In 1996, the book of the Kazakh literary scholar Utegen Kumisbayev "Son of Poland" was published, which is dedicated to the life and creativity of Adolf Yanushkevich, the author of interesting diary notes, created during his long stay in the Kazakh steppes. Separate facts of the translation of Polish fiction works into Kazakh should also be mentioned. In 2006, the publishing house "Amanat" under the guidance of the Kazakh writer Rollan Seisenbayev published a collection of poems by the Polish poet Adam Mickiewicz in the Kazakh language. In 2005, the book "The Well of Three Brothers" with Polish legends in Kazakh and Polish was published in Poznan. The translation into Kazakh was done by Turkic studies students of the Adam Mickiewicz University, the texts were edited by Gulyaikhana Aktai.

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АВТОРСКОЕ «Я» В РАССКАЗЕ «ГЛАМУР В ТРУЩОБАХ» ИЛЬДАРА АБУЗЯРОВА

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THE AUTHOR'S "I" IN THE STORY "GLAMOR IN THE SLUMDS" BY ILDAR ABUZYAROV

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Аннотация

В данной статье рассматривается и анализируется современная в литературе тенденция к предоставлению соотношений между автором, писателем и его героем. Рассмотрен рассказ «Гламур в трущобах» Ильдара Абузьярова с типом авторского «я» – Интровертированный тип авторского «я».

Abstract

This article discusses and analyzes the current trend in literature to provide relationships between the author, writer and his hero. The story "Glamour in the slums" by Ildar Abuzyarov with the type of author's "I" - Introverted type of author's "I" is considered.

Ключевые слова: авторское «я», проза, современный литературный процесс, тип, художественный мир.

Keywords: author's "I", prose, modern literary process, type, artistic world.

В современной литературе появилась такая тенденция к предоставлению соотношений между автором, писателем и его героем. Отношения между ними уже не разграничиваются. Автор уже является героем, также как герой становится автором своего мира. Герой становится и автором, и повествователем, и действующим лицом. В таких произведениях повествование, в большинстве случаев, ведется от первого лица и, следовательно, имеют субъективное осмысление.

В монографии Камиловой С.Э выделяется три типа авторского «я»: «Современные художественные тексты отличаются специфическими особенностями мироздания и, в зависимости от характера

соотношения «Я - мир», исходят из нескольких типов авторского «я»¹:

➤ **Интровертированный тип авторского «я» в современных рассказах**

➤ **Ювенально-ретроспективный тип авторского «я» в современных рассказах**

➤ **Лирический тип авторского «я» в современных русских и узбекских рассказах**

Рассмотрим рассказ Ильдара Абузьярова с первым типом авторского «я». **Интровертированный тип авторского «я».**

«Типического героя как личность, способную на активные действия и поступки, заменяет автор-индивид, замкнутый на самом себе, на своих личностных переживаниях и «маленьких трагедиях»,

¹Камилова С.Э. «Современный рассказ: содержательные векторы и повествовательные стратегии». – Т.: «Fanvatexnologiya», 2016. – С. 132